

Kinetics of V(IV) Catalysed Oxidation of Phenols by Acid Bromate

N. PARIMALA, VIJAYA LAKSHMI and E. V. SUNDARAM

Department of Chemistry, University College, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

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The oxidation of phenol and substituted phenols was studied using KBrO_3 as oxidant in presence of V(IV) in binary solvent mixtures of acetic acid and water. Order with respect to oxidant is one and the order with respect to substrate and the catalyst is found to be fractional. The behaviour of acid shows that the order in acid is different under different acid concentrations. Effects of temperatures and percentage composition of acetic acid were studied. A suitable mechanism in presence of catalyst is given explaining the experimental facts. The effect of substituents was also studied and discussed.

THE oxidation of phenols was studied by different workers using several oxidising agents like iodate¹, periodate², persulphate³⁻⁵, peracetic acid⁶ and hexacyanoferrate(III)⁷. The oxidation of phenol and substituted phenols by bromate in binary solvent mixtures of acetic acid and water was studied by us in detail⁸. A mechanism involving an ion and a dipole in rate determining step was proposed and effect of substituent on this reaction was discussed. In the present study the effect of V(IV) on this reaction is studied under similar conditions. V(IV) seems to be acting as catalyst in this reactions.

Experimental

All the compounds used were of AnalaR grade. The phenols were either distilled or recrystallised just before use to avoid aerial oxidation. Acetic acid was distilled by usual method.

The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted bromate iodometrically. In this reaction mercuric acetate cannot be used for complexing the product Br^- ion⁹. Ortho-quinone was found to be the product as in the case of uncatalysed reaction. The absence of free radicals was confirmed by testing with acrylonitrile.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was studied under pseudo-unimolecular conditions. The concentration of the oxidant was ten times lesser than the phenol concentration. The first order plots i.e., $\log(a-x)$ versus time plots showed non-linearity after about 40% of the reaction was over. The plot was linear upto 40% and then the rate increased considerably. Such type of deviation was not observed in the absence of catalyst⁸. In the case of catalysed reaction, $(a-x)$ was plotted against time and a straight line was observed even upto 70% of the reaction at low concentration of the oxidant. Hence to determine the order with respect to oxidant, experiments were done with different initial bromate concentrations and $(a-x)$ versus time

plots were drawn. Though they are straight lines the slopes were changing. Hence rates were calculated from these plots (Fig. 1). Log rate was plotted against $\log[\text{bromate}]$ and the slope was found to be one. This shows that the order with respect to bromate is one. The deviation in first order plot after 40% of the reaction indicates some complexity in the reaction arising due to catalyst because this complexity was not observed in the absence of catalyst.

Fig. 1. Plot of ΔV against time. Concentration of bromate (A) $1 \times 10^{-3} M$; (B) $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$.

The order with respect to substrate was found to be fractional (Table 1). A plot of $1/k$ versus $1/[\text{phenol}]^{1/2}$ gave a linear plot with an intercept

indicating complex formation between the oxidant and substrate.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE ON THE RATE OF REACTION

$[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.4 M$; $\text{HOAc} = 40\%$;
 $V(\text{IV}) = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\text{temp.} = 30^\circ$.

$\frac{[\text{Phenol}] \times 10^3}{[M]}$	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0	4.0	6.0	8.0
$k \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	1.6	1.9	2.2	2.4	2.6	2.9	3.8	4.2

The order with respect to catalyst was fractional (0.35). This shows that the change in concentration of catalyst does not have much effect on the reaction rate. The rate of catalysed reaction is found to be fourfold over the uncatalysed reaction (Table 2). The fractional order of catalyst indicates that it is involved in the formation of complex. V(IV) can form complex with organic substrates with variable coordination numbers⁹.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF CATALYST ON THE RATE OF REACTION

$[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.4 M$; $\text{HOAc} = 40\%$;
 $[\text{Phenol}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $\text{temp.} = 30^\circ$.

$\frac{[V(\text{IV})] \times 10^5}{[M]}$	0.0	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
$k \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	0.4	0.9	1.2	1.3	1.5	1.6

The catalyst effect can be explained considering that the phenol-V(IV) complex is more reactive than the phenol molecule. The mechanism can be given as:

Scheme 1

or

Scheme 2

In the Scheme 2, V(IV) gets oxidised to V(V) by Br(V) and V(V) in turn oxidises the phenol. If this is the case the reaction should be a free radical one because the oxidation involves one electron transfer. But free radicals are not observed in the reaction mixture because no polymer is produced by the addition of acrylonitrile to the reaction mixture. Hence the catalytic effect of V(IV) may be through Scheme—1. Similarly in the presence of Hg^{2+} the rate of disappearance of bromate increased considerably in the phenol oxidation by bromate⁸.

Phenol- Hg^{2+} complex was proposed by Rao *et al*¹⁰, in the oxidation of phenol by Hg^{2+} . The increase in the rate of oxidation of phenol by bromate in presence of Hg^{2+} indicates that the phenol- Hg^{2+} complex reacts faster than the phenol molecule with bromate.

The rate of oxidation increased on increasing the concentration of sulphuric acid and the data given in Table 3 shows that the dependence of rate on $[\text{H}^+]$ is not simple. Increasing the percentage of acetic acid increased the rate of oxidation. The effect of temperature was studied and the thermodynamic parameters were calculated. The activation energies for catalysed and uncatalysed reactions are 11.4 and 14.7 kcal respectively.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF ACID ON THE RATE OF REACTION

$[\text{BrO}_3^-] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$; $[\text{Phenol}] = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$;
 $[V(\text{IV})] = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$; $\text{HOAc} = 40\%$; $\text{temp.} = 30^\circ$.

$\frac{[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]}{M}$	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.30	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
$k \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	0.6	0.8	0.9	1.1	1.3	1.6	2.5	3.8	5.4

Based on the experimental observations the mechanism is given as in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

From the above mechanism the rate expression obtained is:

$$\frac{-d[\text{BrO}_3^-]}{dt} = k_0 + k' \text{ where as}$$

$$k_0 = \frac{K_1 K_2 k_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{BrO}_3^-] [\text{Phenol}]}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{Phenol}]}$$

$$k' = \frac{K_1 K'_2 K_3 k_4 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{BrO}_3^-] [\text{Phenol}] [V(\text{IV})]}{1 + K_1 K'_2 K_3 [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{Phenol}] [V(\text{IV})]}$$

The effect of substituent was studied and it is observed that electron withdrawing substituents retarded the rate and electron donating substituents increased the rate (Table 4). The correlation of the data was plotted in two ways considering attack of $\text{Br}^+ \text{O}_3$ (1) at hydroxyl oxygen atom and (2) at ortho carbon atom (Fig. 2). The plot showed that the data correlates better when $\log k$ is plotted against σ_m for para and ortho compounds and σ_p

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF SUBSTITUENT ON THE RATE OF REACTION

 $[\text{BrO}_2^-] = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[\text{Phenol}] = 1 \times 10^{-2} M$; $[\text{V(IV)}] = 1 \times 10^{-4} M$; $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 0.4 M$; $\text{HOAc} = 40\%$; $\text{temp.} = 30^\circ$.

Substituent	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	-H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -NO ₂	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
$\frac{k \times 10^3}{\text{min}^{-1}}$	1.60	1.80	2.50	1.90	0.88	0.56	0.49	0.14	0.90	0.76

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k$ against σ , (A) Considering electrophilic attack at hydroxyl oxygen atom. (B) Considering electrophilic attack at ortho carbon atom. Numbering of substituents is as in the Table 4.

for meta compounds. Hence the attack of electrophile was considered to be at ortho carbon atom.

This observation is similar to the observation in the uncatalysed reaction. In the case of nitro phenols, only ortho substituent falls on the line but para and meta substituents are showing much higher rate than expected. The ortho compound behaves differently from para and meta compounds because it shows hydrogen bonding. The high rate of meta and para compounds cannot be explained from the experimental details. Most probably the reason is that V(IV) can also form complex with NO₂ group, hence such complexes formed from para and meta NO₂ phenols are different from rest of the phenols. In the case of *o*-NO₂ phenol such complex formation may not be possible due to steric hindrance.

References

1. D. N. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 756.
2. P. S. RADHAKRISHNA MURTHI, S. C. PATHI and Y. SRIRAMULU, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 955.
3. S. P. SRIVASTAVA and LAKSHMI DATT, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 950.
4. L. D. SHARMA and S. P. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 17.
5. L. D. SHARMA and S. P. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 978.
6. ROGER, A. G. MARSHALL and ROBERT NAYLOR, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin II*, 1974, 1243.
7. P. S. RADHAKRISHNA MURTHI and RAMA KRISHNA PANDA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 1003.
8. VIJAYA LAKSHMI and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 612.
9. W. A. WATERS and J. S. LITTLER, 'Oxidation in Organic Chemistry', Edited by K. B. WIBERG, 1965, 230.
10. V. SURENDER RAO, B. SETHURAM and T. NAVANEETH RAO, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 1291.